

Reducing Latency and Bandwidth Costs in Parallel Sparse Linear Solvers

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Abstract

Parallelizing sparse irregular application on distributed memory systems poses serious scalability challenges due to the communication bottlenecks which manifest themselves in an unpredictable manner as high bandwidth and/or latency overhead. The importance of different components of overall communication cost can be disproportionate due to the irregularity and sparseness inherent in the application. In such conditions, the best strategy for reducing communication overheads should favor the metric that is most crucial for the performance and a general method that attributes same importance to all metrics is likely to suffer. This work takes on the communication challenges offered by the latency-bound irregular applications, i.e., the applications characterized with high number of average and/or maximum messages per processor. The basic idea of our approach is to impose a regular communication pattern onto otherwise irregular communication operations and in this way to provide a low upper bound on the maximum number of messages handled by a processor. Using a regular communication pattern eliminates the irregularity in latency-bound communication operations and necessitates a store-and-forward scheme that consists of multiple stages of communication. Our findings show that the proposed approach is a remedy for the latency-bound applications; it scales seemingly unscalable instances and leads to an average of 50% reduction in parallel runtime on 256 processors.

1. Introduction

Parallelizing iterative solvers for large-scale sparse linear systems on distributed memory machines offers serious scalability challenges due to their low computational intensity, high memory footprint and difficult to avoid communication overheads. A ubiquitous kernel operation found in almost all iterative solvers is the sparse-matrix vector multiplication (SpMV) operation. Since this operation usually constitutes the most time-consuming section of the solver and is performed repeatedly with the same sparsity pattern throughout the iterations, it is vital to obtain an efficient parallelization of it in order to scale the solver. This whitepaper focuses on iterative solvers for sparse symmetric linear systems resulting from irregular applications.

One of the most prominent features of the the irregular applications is that it is difficult to predict the overhead of the communication operations incurred in parallel solve due to the irregular sparsity pattern of the coefficient matrix. This makes efficient parallelization difficult for such applications and scaling them becomes more challenging compared to their regular counterparts. For this reason, there are many intelligent partitioning models proposed in the literature [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]. Many of these partitioning models rely on representing the sparse matrix as a graph and hypergraph and partitioning it for the purpose of parallelization. The irregular applications may also possess other unconventional features such as high latency. Despite the recent works, most

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of the partitioning models in the literature overlook the latency overheads and more than often focus solely on reducing inter-processor communication overhead.

In this whitepaper, we investigate a virtual processor mesh structure in order to bound and reduce the latency overhead besides reducing inter-process communication overhead. The idea is to impose a structured communication pattern onto the irregular communication operations and eliminate the irregularity in these operations, which may manifest themselves as high latency or bandwidth overhead. Assuming a prior partitioning phase is performed –although not necessary– with the aim of reducing inter-process communication our approach then aims to bound the latency overhead at the expense of increasing volume. Specifically, we focus on a two-dimensional virtual processor mesh structure and propose an algorithm to perform irregular point-to-point (P2P) communication operations of parallel SpMV in a structured manner on this topology. In a way, our approach is similar to the partitioning models that obtain a Cartesian distribution [6] [7] [8], with the crucial difference being the proposed method achieves it not in partitioning but in realizing sparse communications. In this manner, it is more flexible and orthogonal in the sense that it does not depend any prior partitioning and is compatible with different partitions on the coefficient matrix. Our approach can be integrated into popular sparse solver libraries such as Trilinos and PETSc.

Our approach necessitates a *store-and-forward* scheme to realize P2P operations in which a processor sends its messages via other processors it directly communicates with. In the mentioned 2D mesh, a processor can directly communicate only with the processors that are in the same row or column with the processor. Hence, for the rest of the processors it needs an indirect communication pattern based on forwarding messages. Such a scheme causes an increase in volume, however, it may drastically reduce the communication overheads of certain applications that are latency-bound and thus improve their scalability.

In our experiments, we compare two extremes for bounding latency overhead with imposing communication patterns. The first is the scheme described above and the second is another scheme that further reduces the latency overhead by bounding it with asymptotically logarithmic complexity. The latter, inherently, causes an even bigger increase in volume. We also include a common baseline that only aims at reducing total volume of communication. Among these three, we show that the proposed scheme can strike a very good trade-off between bandwidth and latency overheads in certain cases. Our results indicate that achieving exascale performance necessitates addressing as many components as possible and finding a balance between these components.

The rest of this work is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the necessary background and in addition describes the first baseline tested in our experiments. Section 3 describes how to realize P2P communication operations in the solver within the 2D virtual processor mesh. Section 4 presents the experimental evaluation. Section 5 concludes.

2. Background

2.1. Partitioning of the coefficient matrix

We assume the coefficient matrix A of size $n \times n$ is rowwise partitioned among K processors for the parallelization of the SpMV operation $y = Ax$ and hence the sparse iterative solver containing it. As we focus on the linear solvers for sparse symmetric systems, we assume a conformal partition on the vectors of the solvers, i.e., they are all partitioned according to the partition on A . Given the partition on A , the matrix can be permuted into a block structure as follows:

$$A_{block} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & \cdots & A_{1K} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{K1} & \cdots & A_{KK} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Without loss of generality, we assume that processor P_k is held responsible for the computations on submatrix blocks A_{k1}, \dots, A_{kK} that altogether constitute the k th row stripe of size $n_k \times n$ and the linear vector operations on the subvectors x_k, y_k and other vectors in the solver, that is, processor P_k is responsible for computing the SpMV of the form $y_k = A_{k1}x_1 + \cdots + A_{kK}x_K$. A submatrix block A_{kl} is called diagonal if $k = l$ and off-diagonal otherwise. The proposed methods in this work apply to a columnwise partitioning of A as well.

There are several ways to obtain a partitioning of A with graph and hypergraph partitioning models being the most popular ones among them. These models usually aim at reducing the total volume of communication incurred in parallel SpMV operations. The proposed methods in this work do not depend on any of these models and they are compatible with any partition of A as long as they are one-dimensional, i.e., the smallest indivisible unit of computational task is defined on the rows or columns of A . Nonetheless, we use the hypergraph partitioner PaToH [2] to partition A as it is shown to be an efficient tool for reducing volume, and for the

proposed methods, the lower the communication volume the better as they increase the volume in favor of reducing the number of messages.

2.2. Row-parallel multiplication

We next review the row-parallel matrix-vector multiplies as this algorithm serves the basis for our implementation and it is the baseline scheme for our comparisons in experiments (as is used in the solver). Considering the SpMV of the form $y = Ax$, the processor P_k is responsible for the k th row stripe of A and the subvectors x_k and y_k , which are conformal. The steps of the row-parallel algorithm for P_k are then as follows:

- For each submatrix block A_{lk} where $l \neq k$, send x_k^l to processor P_l . The sparse subvector x_k^l here contains the elements needed by P_l from P_k and correspond to the nonzero column segments in A_{lk} .
- Perform the local matrix-vector multiplication $y_k^k = A_{kk} \times x_k$. This operation does not necessitate communication and is overlapped with the incoming x -vector elements that P_k needs for computations regarding off-diagonal blocks it owns.
- Set $y_k = y_k^k$.
- For each off-diagonal block A_{kl} , receive x_l^k from processor P_l and compute $y_k^l = A_{kl} \times x_l^k$ and update vector y with $y_k = y_k + y_k^l$. In a similar manner to the first step, the sparse subvector x_l^k here contains the elements needed by P_k from P_l and correspond to the nonzero column segments in A_{kl} .

In the algorithm above, there is a single communication phase prior to computations in which the elements of x are communicated between processors. This communication phase necessitates sending of the same elements of x to multiple processors, which is referred to as expand operations.

3. SpMV on two-dimensional virtual processor mesh

The basic motivation of imposing a virtual two-dimensional (2D) processor mesh on point-to-point communication between processors is to be able to limit the maximum number of messages communicated. This, of course, is an attempt towards reducing the latency overhead which may be useful for applications that are latency-bound. For example, in the row-parallel algorithm, there is no restriction on processors' communication pattern and any processor may communicate to any other in the system. This, in the worst case, may lead to a maximum of $K - 1$ messages per processor, i.e., $O(K)$. The idea for bounding maximum number of messages is to impose a virtual 2D processor mesh of size $K = P \times Q$ and restrict the processors to communicate only to the processors in the same row and column of the mesh with subject processor. In this way, the maximum number of messages communicated becomes $(P - 1) + (Q - 1)$ at worst, i.e., $O(2(\lceil\sqrt{K}\rceil - 1)) = O(\sqrt{K})$. This may lead to tremendous reductions in communication overhead depending on whether the application is latency-bound and can improve the scalability of the target application drastically.

Figure 1 illustrates a virtual processor mesh of size $P \times Q = 4 \times 4$ for a total of $K = 16$ processors. The communication operations along column and row dimension of the processor mesh are respectively shown in Figure 1(b) and Figure 1(c). Observe that although a processor may necessitate a direct communication with a processor that is not in its own row or column, the structure of the 2D processor mesh disallows this direct communication in order to bound the maximum number of messages. Such cases necessitate a *store-and-forward* scheme in which the indirect communication operations are performed with the help of the processors that are in the same row or column of the processor. For example in Figure 1, if P_5 has certain vector elements to send to P_3 , it first sends them to P_1 (which is in the same column with P_5) in the communication operations along the column. These vector elements are then *stored* by P_1 , and they are *forwarded* to target processor P_3 (which is in the same row with P_1) in the communication operations along the row. The communications between the processors along the same row or column can be performed directly and do not necessitate any store-and-forward. Note that the communication operations could first have been performed along the row dimension and then the column dimension, which necessitates a dual and similar communication pattern to the one mentioned above. We focus only on the former pattern for the ease of presentation.

Figure 1: A virtual processor mesh and the communication pattern induced by it. The communications along column and row dimensions are indicated with the processors that are in same color.

Performing P2P communications of parallel SpMV operations on a 2D virtual processor mesh necessitates a two-stage communication scheme. The first stage is assumed to be along the column dimension of the processor mesh and incurs a maximum of $P - 1$ messages. The second stage is assumed to be along the row dimension of the processor mesh and incurs a maximum of $Q - 1$ messages. Since some communications cannot be performed directly and necessitate a store-and-forward scheme, this incurs extra communication volume compared to the base scheme in which the processors can communicate directly, i.e., such as in the row-parallel algorithm described in Section 2.2. On 2D processor mesh, there can only be a single extra “hop”, i.e., the contents of a message can be stored and forwarded at most once. Hence, if total communication volume is V_b in base row-parallel algorithm, and in the worst case if all messages necessitate to be stored and forwarded, the total communication volume can be at most $2V_b$ on 2D processor mesh. On the other extreme, if none of the messages need to be stored and forwarded, i.e., all communications can be performed directly among the processors in either row or column dimension, then there is no extra volume overhead and the total communication volume is equal to that of base row-parallel algorithm, i.e., V_b . Therefore, the total communication volume V_m on 2D mesh is

$$V_b \leq V_m \leq 2V_b.$$

Another aspect of the store-and-forward scheme that is different from the base row-parallel algorithm is that it necessitates auxiliary buffers to be maintained across stages of the communication. In the base row-parallel algorithm, the communication operations can be performed directly on the elements of the vectors x and y . The communication operations on 2D mesh still utilize communication on these vectors as well, however, they also require two extra buffers (one for store and another for forward) due to indirect communications that may occur between processors.

The pseudo-code for parallel SpMV on a 2D virtual processor mesh is given in Figure 2. The auxiliary buffers used by the processors are named as `stbuf` and `fwbuf`. Let $\text{SendSet}(P_k)$ denote the original processors P_k communicates with in the row-parallel algorithm. This set is divided into three disjoint sets as $\text{COLPROCS}(P_k)$, $\text{ROWPROCS}(P_k)$ and $\text{IDRPROCS}(P_k)$. The set $\text{COLPROCS}(P_k)$ denotes the processors that P_k sends a message to and that are in the same column with P_k . Similarly, the set $\text{ROWPROCS}(P_k)$ denotes the processors that P_k sends a message to and that are in the same row with P_k . These two sets contain the processors that P_k can directly communicate with. The set $\text{IDRPROCS}(P_k)$ denotes the processors that P_k indirectly communicates with and thus needs to send the corresponding messages with the help of the other processors. In Figure 1, for example, if $\text{SendSet}(P_5) = \{P_1, P_3, P_4, P_9, P_{14}\}$, then $\text{COLPROCS}(P_k) = \{P_1, P_9\}$, $\text{ROWPROCS}(P_k) = \{P_4\}$ and $\text{IDRPROCS}(P_k) = \{P_3, P_{14}\}$. Note that $\text{SendSet}(P_k) = \text{COLPROCS}(P_k) \cup \text{ROWPROCS}(P_k) \cup \text{IDRPROCS}(P_k)$.

For the first stage of the communication operations, i.e., the operations for the communication along column dimension, P_k first fills its forward buffer by processing the processors in $\text{COLPROCS}(P_k) \cup \text{IDRPROCS}(P_k)$. The messages to these processors either require forwarding or they directly belong to the processors in the column of P_k . P_k also writes the header information and x -vector elements into this buffer. The header information regarding processors is necessary since the receiving processor must know to which processor the message is going to be forwarded. The corresponding locations in the forward buffer are given by P_l/Q , where P_l is a processor in the respective set. Then, P_k checks all the processors in its column and if it needs to communicate with them it sends the respective elements of x -vector along with the header information. Then, P_k

performs the matrix-vector multiply on its diagonal block. This computation can be performed without any communication and it is overlapped with communication operations of the first stage. P_k then waits its store buffer to be filled with the messages from the processors that are in the same column with it and empties its forward buffer to use it again.

```

SPMV_MESH_2D (A, x, y, K, P, Q)
  stbuf[0...max(P, Q)-1][]      // store buffer (ragged array)
  fwbuf[0...max(P, Q)-1][]      // forward buffer (ragged array)
  myrowdim = P/Q
  mycoldim = P%Q

  // Communication operations along column dimension
  foreach  $P_l$  in COLPROCS( $P_k$ ) U IDRPROCS( $P_k$ )
    fwbuf[ $P_l/Q$ ] = fwbuf[ $P_l/Q$ ] U ( $P_l, x_k^l$ )

  for p = 0 to P-1
    if fwbuf[p] not empty
      SEND fwbuf[p] to processor (p*Q)+mycoldim

  // Local SpMV
   $y_k^k = A_{kk} \times x_k$ 
  Set  $y_k = y_k^k$ 

  Wait for my stbuf to be filled
  Empty fwbuf

  // Process store buffer and form forward buffer
  for p = 0 to P-1
    from = (p*Q) + mycoldim
    foreach ( $P_l, x_{from}^l$ ) in stbuf[p]
      if  $P_l \neq P_k$ 
        fwbuf[ $P_l\%Q$ ] = fwbuf[ $P_l\%Q$ ] U ( $P_{from}, x_{from}^l$ )

  foreach  $P_l$  in ROWPROCS( $P_k$ )
    fwbuf[ $P_l\%Q$ ] = fwbuf[ $P_l\%Q$ ] U ( $P_k, x_k^l$ )

  // Communication operations along row dimension
  for q = 0 to Q-1
    if fwbuf[q] not empty
      SEND fwbuf[q] to processor (myrowdim*Q)+q

  Wait for my stbuf to be filled

  // Non-local SpMV
  for q = 0 to Q-1
    foreach ( $P_l, x_l^k$ ) in stbuf[p]
       $y_k = y_k + A_{kl} \times x_l^k$ 

```

Figure 2: The pseudo-code as run by processor P_k with the store-and-forward scheme on 2D processor mesh.

Prior to the second stage of the communication operations, i.e., the operations for the communication along row dimension, P_k must process the contents of the store buffer and arrange the contents of the forward buffer

accordingly. This resembles to a shuffle-like operation as the contents of the messages that will be sent to a specific processor in the same row with P_k are scattered in the store buffer. P_k processes the contents of the store buffer for each processor that are in the same column with it and if the destination of the message is not itself, it appends it to the respective forward buffer location using the header information found in the contents of the message. It then appends any messages it can directly send to the processors in the same row with itself by using $\text{ROWPROCS}(P_k)$. The corresponding locations in the forward buffer are given by $P_l \% Q$, where P_l is a processor in the respective set. Then, P_k checks all the processors in its row and if it needs to communicate with them it sends the respective elements of x -vector along with the header information. P_k then waits its store buffer to be filled with the messages from the processors that are in the same row with it and for each such message received message, it checks the contents and gets the x -vector elements and performs its non-local SpMV with the received elements.

Figure 3: An example concerning the vector elements to be sent by P_5 on a 4×4 mesh.

The example in Figure 3 depicts the communication stages of store-and-forward scheme for P_5 on a 4×4 processor mesh. The processors that need vector elements from P_5 are $\text{SendSet}(P_5) = \{P_1, P_3, P_4, P_7, P_8, P_{10}, P_{13}\}$. These processors are colored in red in the left portion of the figure indicating they have not received corresponding elements yet. Regarding the example, note that $\text{COLPROCS}(P_5) = \{P_1, P_{13}\}$, $\text{ROWPROCS}(P_5) = \{P_4, P_7\}$ and $\text{IDRPROCS}(P_5) = \{P_3, P_8, P_{10}\}$. In the first communication stage along the column dimension, P_5 sends messages to P_1 , P_9 and P_{13} whose contents respectively include $\{x_5^1, x_5^3\}$, $\{x_5^8, x_5^{10}\}$ and $\{x_5^{13}\}$. The processors P_1 and P_{13} directly receive their vector elements from P_5 . The processors that receive their x -vector elements are colored in green. Then in the second communication stage along the row dimension, P_1 forwards x_5^3 to P_3 , P_9 forwards x_5^8 to P_8 and x_5^{10} to P_{10} , and P_5 itself sends x_5^4 to P_4 and x_5^7 to P_7 . After these operations, all messages reach their destination.

4. Experimental evaluation

4.1. Setup

We evaluate three schemes in our experiments:

- The baseline row-parallel algorithm, denoted with BL. This serves as the baseline for the proposed scheme. In this scheme, the coefficient matrix is partitioned with the aim of reducing inter-processor communication. Hence, this only addresses reducing bandwidth costs. This is one of the most common partitioning models used in the literature and is realized by many graph/hypergraph partitioners. In our case, we represent the matrix with column-net hypergraph model [2] and use PaToH to obtain partitions.
- The scheme in which P2P communications are performed assuming a 2D virtual processor mesh, denoted with M2D. After the matrix is partitioned as in BL, in the solver in SpMV the communications are realized as described in Section 3. Hence, this scheme reduces bandwidth and latency costs, the former in the partitioning phase and the latter in realizing communication operations. Reducing latency costs has the effect of increasing volume obtained after the partitioning phase, however, this is a trade-off this scheme aims to exploit.
- The scheme in which P2P communications are performed with the communication pattern of bidirectional exchange algorithm, denoted with BDE. After the matrix is partitioned as in BL, in the

solver in SpMV the communications are realized as described in [9]. This scheme also reduces bandwidth and latency costs like M2D, however, it takes on a more aggressive approach while doing so as both the average and maximum number of messages is $O(\log K)$, while in M2D, the maximum number of messages is $O(\sqrt{K})$. BDE causes a greater increase in volume compared to M2D due to this aggressive approach.

matrix	kind	#rows/#cols	#nnzs	avg	min	max	stdev	cv
144	undirected graph	144649	2148786	14.86	4	26	2.7	0.18
598a	undirected graph	110971	1483868	13.37	5	26	2.9	0.22
case39	power network problem sequence	40216	1042160	25.91	1	20024	316.2	12.2
crystk03	materials	24696	1751178	70.91	24	81	14.2	0.20
fe_rotor	undirected graph	99617	1324862	13.30	5	125	3.9	0.29
gas_sensor	model reduction	66917	1703365	25.45	8	33	3.5	0.14
H2O	theoretical/quantum chemistry	67024	2216736	33.07	14	37	4.8	0.15
net125	optimization	36720	2577200	70.19	3	231	66.6	0.95
opt1	structural	15449	1930655	125.00	44	243	42.5	0.34
pcrystk03	duplicate materials	24696	1751178	70.91	24	81	14.2	0.20
pkustk07	structural	16860	2418804	143.50	39	267	61.1	0.43
raefsky4	structural	19779	1328611	67.17	18	177	16.0	0.24
ramage02	computational fluid dynamics	16830	2866352	170.30	45	270	52.9	0.31
TSOPF_FS_b162_c4	power network	40798	2398220	58.78	1	20054	495.5	8.43
wave	2D/3D	156317	2118662	13.55	3	44	3.3	0.24

Table 1: Properties of test matrices

We test these three schemes for two different number of processors $K = 64$ and $K = 256$. For M2D, for 64 processors a 8×8 virtual processor mesh and for 256 processors a 16×16 virtual processor mesh is assumed. The system we used in our experiments is an IBM System x iDataPlex system (SuperMUC). Each node consists of 16 cores, clocked at 2.70 GHz, and 32 GB of memory.

We implemented the conjugate gradient solver in C using MPI for inter-process communication. The results given in this section regarding the time values only constitute the SpMV operation in the solver to better clarify the comparison between three schemes as these schemes aim at improving performance of the SpMV kernel alone. We included a warmup phase in our experiments. The solver is repeated 1000 times and a single SpMV time is reported in the following sections.

All three schemes are tested with 15 symmetric matrices from University of Florida Sparse Matrix Collection [10]. The number of nonzeros regarding these matrices vary from one to three million. Various properties of these matrices are given in Table 1. The columns “avg”, “min” and “max” denote average, minimum and maximum number of nonzeros in a row or column. The column “stdev” is the standard deviation of number of nonzeros in rows or columns. The last column “cv” stands for coefficient of variation and again belongs to the number of nonzeros in rows or columns. The last two columns are usually good indicators of irregularity of the sparseness in the matrix, meaning the higher the values in these two columns, the more likely the matrix is more irregular.

4.2. Results

Tables 2 and 3 present the communication statistics and the parallel SpMV times of the three schemes at $K = 64$ and $K = 256$, respectively. The columns “vavg”, “mavg” and “mmax” respectively denote the average volume, average number of messages and maximum number of messages. The volume and message statistics are in terms of sent data. The SpMV time is in microseconds. The last row contains the geometrically averaged normalized values of M2D and BDE with respect to those of BL. For example, in the last row of Table 3, a value of 1.39 indicates that on the average volume of M2D is 39% higher than that of BL.

matrix	vavg			mavg			mmax			parallel time (usec)		
	BL	BDE	M2D	BL	BDE	M2D	BL	BDE	M2D	BL	BDE	M2D
144	763	1533	989	10.1	6	8.3	24	6	13	111	108	101
598a	590	1084	736	8.3	6	6.9	19	6	12	74	76	67
case39	3498	11482	6424	28.0	6	10.5	63	6	14	490	255	202
crystk03	481	823	580	7.9	6	6.8	13	6	10	67	74	65
fe_rotor	498	955	640	9.5	6	7.9	36	6	13	80	74	63
gas_sensor	555	1133	723	9.5	6	7.9	15	6	11	73	80	68
H2O	2826	6235	3965	15.8	6	9.7	30	6	13	119	131	102
net125	3029	8522	4848	28.4	6	11.6	55	6	14	189	170	137
opt1	421	852	534	6.9	6	6.3	16	6	11	73	81	70
pcrystk03	481	823	580	7.9	6	6.8	13	6	10	68	75	66
pkustk07	700	1555	928	11.7	6	8.6	23	6	14	104	97	90
raefsky4	373	726	455	6.4	6	6.1	12	6	10	52	65	54
ramage02	727	1627	982	11.5	6	8.6	25	6	14	122	108	102
TSOPF_FS_b162_c4	4872	15742	8859	28.5	6	10.5	63	6	14	533	347	268
wave	889	1822	1194	11.4	6	9.2	22	6	13	94	100	92
<i>normalized wrt BL (geomean)</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>2.17</i>	<i>1.37</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.51</i>	<i>0.70</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.25</i>	<i>0.50</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.96</i>	<i>0.82</i>

Table 2: Communication statistics and parallel SpMV time of three schemes on 64 processors (vavg: average volume, mavg: average number of messages, mmax: maximum number of messages – all in terms of sent data).

matrix	vavg			mavg			mmax			parallel time (usec)		
	BL	BDE	M2D	BL	BDE	M2D	BL	BDE	M2D	BL	BDE	M2D
144	367	841	463	10.4	8	9.9	34	8	22	102	71	57
598a	295	685	365	10.3	8	9.8	32	8	22	80	68	51
case39	959	4185	1765	30.2	8	12.3	224	8	30	921	164	158
crystk03	282	712	359	12.7	8	10.9	24	8	19	57	68	46
fe_rotor	268	649	330	11.9	8	11.0	34	8	25	71	66	51
gas_sensor	304	740	388	11.6	8	10.8	25	8	19	57	67	46
H2O	1400	3759	1962	26.8	8	17.3	44	8	25	207	97	79
net125	1440	5983	2521	69.5	8	22.0	129	8	28	696	136	122
opt1	292	758	379	11.6	8	10.6	31	8	20	88	70	51
pcrystk03	282	712	359	12.7	8	10.9	24	8	19	59	66	45
pkustk07	427	1266	607	18.2	8	13.9	38	8	23	115	84	68
raefsky4	226	564	286	10.7	8	9.6	25	8	18	67	67	41
ramage02	456	1315	644	18.4	8	14.0	35	8	25	109	86	66
TSOPF_FS_b162_c4	2271	9830	4219	50.5	8	15.3	230	8	30	1015	269	198
wave	416	1044	540	12.8	8	12.0	29	8	23	64	75	55
<i>normalized wrt BL (geomean)</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>2.83</i>	<i>1.39</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.46</i>	<i>0.71</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.18</i>	<i>0.52</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.66</i>	<i>0.50</i>

Table 3: Communication statistics and parallel SpMV time of three schemes on 256 processors (vavg: average volume, mavg: average number of messages, mmax: maximum number of messages – all in terms of sent data).

In terms of communication statistics, average volume is crucial for bandwidth costs while average and maximum number of messages are crucial for the latency costs. When we compare three schemes in terms of bandwidth costs, it is seen that BL obtains the best results, followed by M2D and then BDE. This is expected as M2D and BDE favor latency costs at the expense of bandwidth costs. M2D causes an increase of 37-39% in average volume while BDE causes an increase of 117-183% in average volume. BDE's worst performance in this metric is due to its drastically lower message count statistics. When three schemes are compared in terms of average and maximum number of messages, it is seen that BDE performs the best, followed by M2D and then BL. BDE achieves drastically lower maximum number of messages compared to BL, 4-5x lower. M2D is also able to halve the maximum number of messages compared to BL.

When three schemes are compared in terms of parallel SpMV time, the best performing scheme is clearly M2D. This is due to the fact that this scheme achieves a trade-off between bandwidth and latency costs and hence is able to reduce the parallel runtime by 18% at $K = 64$ and 50% at $K = 256$. Recall that M2D is second to BL in bandwidth costs and it is second to BDE in latency costs.

Especially in difficult instances with a higher irregularity (such as the matrices case39 and TSOPF_FS_b162_c4, see “cv” column in Table 1), M2D leads to drastic improvements in runtime being 5-7x faster compared to BL at 256 processors. Moreover, it improves scalability in these cases. For example, BL’s parallel SpMV runtime for TSOPF_FS_b162_c4 is 533 usecs at $K = 64$ and 1015 usecs at $K = 256$, while M2D’s parallel SpMV runtime for the same matrix is 268 usecs at $K = 64$ and 198 usecs at $K = 256$. These values for BDE are respectively 347 and 269 usecs. Both M2D and BDE are able to scale the matrices that are otherwise not scalable when using BL. The relatively low efficiency is due to the small instances used in the experiments. Most instances have around 5,000 to 20,000 nonzeros per processor at $K = 256$. Larger instances would have better efficiency as they accommodate more computation.

5. Conclusions

We proposed a novel two-phase scheme to reduce the bandwidth and latency overheads in parallel solvers on distributed systems. In the first phase a common partitioner is used to address the bandwidth overheads and in the second phase, the P2P communication operations in the iterative solver are realized with a communication pattern that assumes a two-dimensional virtual processor mesh. Using a regular pattern to realize P2P communications allows us to bound the latency overhead with message count proportional to the square root of the number of processors in the system. Although our approach increases the bandwidth overheads slightly due to the store-and-forward scheme to realize communication operations on the virtual processor mesh, the drastic improvements in the latency costs lead to an average of 50% reduction in parallel SpMV time on 256 processors.

As future work, we consider generalizing our scheme to more general cases with variable number of phases. This has the potential of further improvements since the investigated schemes examine the two extreme ends and does not consider the cases in between. We also wish to benefit from using neighbour communicators in MPI.

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